

**COSMETIC TOXICITY AND DUSHIVISHA: AN AYURVEDIC APPROACH TO
MODERN BEAUTY HAZARDS****Anisha Jain^{*1}, Ritu Kapoor², Manoj Adlakha³, Kiran Kamaliya⁴, Vaibhav Narwade⁵**¹Post Graduate Scholar, P.G. Department of Agad Tantra, PGIA, Dr. S. R. Rajasthan Ayurved University, Jodhpur, Rajasthan, India.²H.O.D. & Professor, P.G. Department of Agad Tantra, PGIA, Dr. S. R. Rajasthan Ayurved University, Jodhpur, Rajasthan, India.³Associate Professor, Department of Dravya Guna, PGIA, Dr. S. R. Rajasthan Ayurved University, Jodhpur, Rajasthan, India.⁴Post Graduate Scholar, P.G. Department of Agad Tantra, PGIA, Dr. S. R. Rajasthan Ayurved University, Jodhpur, Rajasthan, India.⁵Post Graduate Scholar, P.G. Department of Agad Tantra, PGIA, Dr. S. R. Rajasthan Ayurved University, Jodhpur, Rajasthan, India.***Corresponding Author: Anisha Jain**

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20020733>**How to cite this Article:** Anisha Jain^{*1}, Ritu Kapoor², Manoj Adlakha³, Kiran Kamaliya⁴, Vaibhav Narwade⁵ (2026). Cosmetic Toxicity And Dushivisha: An Ayurvedic Approach To Modern Beauty Hazards. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(5), 205–208.

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Article Received on 05/04/2026

Article Revised on 25/04/2026

Article Published on 01/05/2026

ABSTRACT

Cosmetic products are widely used for enhancing beauty and personal care, but they often contain harmful chemicals that can accumulate in the body over time, leading to chronic health issues. This article explores the concept of Dushivisha (latent toxins) in Ayurveda and its correlation with the cumulative toxicity of cosmetics. It highlights the correlation between Dushivisha and cosmetic toxicity and importance of understanding and managing cosmetic toxicity through Ayurvedic principles, including detoxification, herbal remedies, dushivishari agad and lifestyle adjustments.

KEYWORDS: Cosmetic toxicity, Dushivisha, Ayurveda, detoxification, chronic health issues, natural remedies**INTRODUCTION**

In recent times, it become a common practice to use cosmetic products on regular basis by the women of all age groups across the globe. Presence of toxic elements at higher levels in cosmetic products are one of the main exposure routes to the humans that causes significant health concerns. As we know that cosmetics have direct application on the skin, therefore consumers are at higher risk of toxic element exposure. Generally, the structure of the skin act as the first protective lining that inhibits the entrance of toxicants into the internal tissues. However, these toxic elements can either be adsorb or absorb through the skin and enter into the blood due to the long-term exposure. To produce beautifying and attractive color in cosmetic products, various colored elemental compounds are frequently used by manufacturer, which create adverse impact on the consumer's skin. In addition, cosmetic contains many

components that can cause several dermal allergic reactions i.e., eczemas, damage the texture of skin and dermatitis. Several toxic elements for example mercury, chromium, lead, cobalt, arsenic, nickel and cadmium are of the major concern as they can produce several skin problems and other physiological disorders. However, the prolonged use of these products can lead to the accumulation of harmful chemicals. Ayurveda, the ancient science of life, offers valuable insights into managing such chemical toxicities through its holistic approach.

Understanding Cosmetic Toxicity

Modern lifestyles often involve extensive use of cosmetics for enhancing appearance. These products, including skin creams, lotions, cleansers, body washes, nail polishes, and deodorants, contain numerous chemicals like active substances, colorants,

preservatives, coal tar, dyes, preservatives, and heavy metals that can be absorbed through the skin, leading to various health issues such as skin disorders, allergies, and hormonal imbalances. The concept of cumulative toxicity, where the effects of these chemicals build up over time, aligns with the Ayurvedic concept of Dushivisha. According to a study published in the Journal of Applied Toxicology, certain cosmetic products were found to contain harmful substances like parabens, phthalates, and formaldehyde, which can pose significant health risks upon prolonged exposure. Prolonged use of these chemicals can lead to the accumulation of toxins in the body, contributing to conditions similar to Dushivisha.

Dushivisha

Dushivisha a type of poison that vitiates Dhatus (body tissues) due to factors like habitat (Desha), season (Kaala), diet, and day-time sleeping habits. It includes poisons from plants (Sthavara), animals (Jangma), and artificial sources (Kritrima) that remain partially in the body, weakened by antidotes, or become less potent due to exposure to fire, wind, and sun. Enveloped by Kapha (one of the three doshas), these poisons can persist in the body for years without proving fatal due to their mild strength.

Dushivisha refers to the accumulation of toxins in the body that manifest gradually, causing chronic ailments. These toxins are not immediately lethal but remain dormant in the body, leading to a slow deterioration of health. According to Ayurveda, these toxins can result from environmental pollutants, improper diet, lifestyle choices, and the use of cosmetics. The slow-acting nature of Dushivisha makes it challenging to diagnose and treat.

Avayaktavastha (Latent Phase of Dushivisha): With reduced potency, Dushivisha doesn't cause immediate fatality and remains hidden by Kapha for years, showing no immediate symptoms.

Aggravation Factors: Dushivisha can flare up on cloudy days or with exposure to cold and wind.

Purvroopa (Prodromal Symptoms): When about to flare up, Dushivisha may cause sleepiness, heaviness, yawning, joint looseness, goosebumps, and body aches.

Roopa (Manifested Symptoms): Affected individuals may experience diarrhea, skin discoloration, thirst, anorexia, fainting, vomiting, stammering, vertigo, and symptoms of dusyodara. It also causes pustules, Kitibha, and urticarial rashes.

Impact on the Body Dushivisha results in intoxication after meals, indigestion, anorexia, circular skin patches, urticaria, mental confusion, tissue depletion (Dhatukashya), facial and limb edema, ascites, vomiting, diarrhea, skin discoloration, fainting, intermittent high fever, and unquenchable thirst. Some poisons cause

insanity, abdominal distension, semen depletion (Shukra Kshya), muffled voice, and various skin disorders (Kustha).

Ayurvedic Approach to Managing Cosmetic Toxicity (Dushi Visha Chikitsa)

According to Ashtang Hrudaya Uttarsthan, the treatment for Dushivisha (cumulative toxins) begins with Swedana (Sudation) as a preparatory procedure (Purvakarma). This is followed by Vaman (therapeutic emesis) and Virechana (therapeutic purgation) as the main procedures (Pradhan Karma). After these detoxification processes, Dushivishari Agada is administered with honey (Madhu) to counteract the residual toxins.

Dushivishari Agada is a potent herbal formulation that includes: Pipalli (Piper longum) that Enhances digestion and metabolism, Dhyamak (Vetiveria zizanioides) Known for its cooling properties and stress relief, Jatamansi (Nardostachys jatamansi) Supports mental health and acts as a calming agent, Lodhra (Symplocos racemosa) Useful in treating inflammation and skin disorders, Ela (Elettaria cardamomum) Acts as a digestive aid and has antimicrobial properties, Suvarchika (Gynandropis pentaphylla) Known for its detoxifying effects, Musta (Cyperus rotundus) Helps in digestive disorders and promotes liver health, Tagar (Tabernaemontana divaricata) Known for its sedative and anxiolytic properties, Kushtha (Saussurea lappa) Beneficial for respiratory and skin health, Yashtimadhu (Glycyrrhiza glabra) Acts as an anti-inflammatory and expectorant, Chandan (Santalum album) Offers cooling and anti-inflammatory benefits, Gairik (Red ochre/Ferrous oxide) Known for its astringent and absorbent properties.

Diet and Lifestyle Adjustments:

- **Balanced Diet:** Emphasizing fresh, organic foods and avoiding processed items.
- **Hydration:** Drinking adequate water and herbal teas to flush out toxins.
- **Regular Exercise:** Practicing yoga and pranayama (breathing exercises) to enhance circulation and promote detoxification.
- **Rest and Relaxation:** Ensuring sufficient rest and reducing stress through meditation and relaxation techniques.

DISCUSSION

Toxicity measures how harmful a substance can be to humans or animals. Chronic toxicity refers to the harmful effects of a substance over an extended period, typically due to repeated or continuous exposure. In the context of cosmetics, some ingredients are not fully eliminated from the body, leading to cumulative toxicity. Prolonged exposure to these substances can produce clinical features similar to those described by Acharya Sushrut for Dushivisha. According to Acharya Sushrut, Dushivisha results in various symptoms such as indigestion, anorexia, skin eruptions, urticaria, mental confusion,

tissue depletion (Dhatukashya), facial and limb edema, ascites, vomiting, diarrhea, skin discoloration, fainting, intermittent high fever, and unquenchable thirst. It can also cause insanity, abdominal distension, semen depletion (Shukra Kshaya), muffled voice, and various skin disorders (Kustha). The long-term use of cosmetics, containing a range of chemicals, can lead to various toxic effects and complications. These include respiratory irritation, nervous disturbances, contact dermatitis, allergies, skin DNA damage, skin cancer, asthma, ovarian cancer, endocrine disruptions, and developmental problems.

Understanding the parallels between Dushivisa and the effects of chronic cosmetic toxicity underscores the need for safer cosmetic products and holistic approaches to detoxification and health management.

CONCLUSION

Dushivisa can be effectively correlated with cumulative toxicity, as it refers to the gradual accumulation of toxins in the body, leading to harmful effects over time. Unlike acute poisoning, Dushivisa manifests slowly, affecting various systems such as the skin, gastrointestinal tract, and nervous system. The prolonged use of cosmetics, laden with chemicals, parallels this concept, as it can lead to severe long-term health issues. To mitigate these effects, it is crucial to adopt a cautious approach towards the use of cosmetics. By understanding the principles of Dushivisa and implementing Ayurvedic practices like detoxification, herbal remedies, dushivishari agad and lifestyle modifications, we can significantly reduce the risk of chronic toxicity. Ayurveda's holistic approach offers invaluable insights for achieving long-term health and wellness in the modern world, emphasizing the importance of mindful and judicious use of cosmetic products to avoid their detrimental impact on the body.

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